

Article Title:

Discovering a New Rule in Multiplication of Natural

Numbers Author:

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Province Abstract: This research demonstrates a new rule in the operation of multiplying natural numbers that has not been mentioned in existing mathematical sources. The aim of this study is to identify and examine the features of this rule and explore the possibility of generalizing it to larger sets of numbers. Preliminary results indicate that this pattern holds across a wide range of natural numbers and can be used in elementary mathematics

Education Introduction: Multiplication is one of the four basic operations in mathematics, taught from the early years. In recent years, children's and teenagers' interest in discovering new numerical patterns has increased. In this study, the author, through daily mathematics exercises, has noticed an interesting rule in the multiplication of natural numbers that has not previously appeared in textbooks or official

sources Research Method: In this research, by repeatedly examining the products of different pairs of natural numbers and comparing the results with their sums and differences, a new pattern was observed. Then, to ensure the validity of this pattern, experiments were conducted on More than 100 numerical samples were conducted and the results were recorded, with the results randomly presented below.

Findings : The discovered law is stated as follows: If two equal natural numbers a are multiplied together and the result is the number b , then the product of the two numbers $(a+1)$ and $(a-1)$ equals $(b-1)$. If $a \times a = b$, then $(a - 1) \times (a + 1) = b - 1$ Proof of the principle:

$$\begin{aligned} a \times a = b &\Rightarrow (a-1) \times (a+1) = b - 1 \\ a^2 - 1 &= b - 1 \\ a^2 - 1 + 1 &= b - 1 + 1 \\ a^2 &= b \quad \Rightarrow \quad a \times a = b \end{aligned}$$

for example:

$1 \times 1 = 1 \Rightarrow 0 \times 2 = 0$	$10 \times 10 = 100 \Rightarrow 9 \times 11 = 99$	$34 \times 34 = 1156 \Rightarrow 33 \times 35 = 1155$
$2 \times 2 = 4 \Rightarrow 1 \times 3 = 3$	$11 \times 11 = 121 \Rightarrow 10 \times 12 = 120$	$47 \times 47 = 2209 \Rightarrow 46 \times 48 = 2208$
$3 \times 3 = 9 \Rightarrow 2 \times 4 = 8$	$12 \times 12 = 144 \Rightarrow 11 \times 13 = 143$	$56 \times 56 = 3136 \Rightarrow 55 \times 57 = 3135$
$4 \times 4 = 16 \Rightarrow 3 \times 5 = 15$	$13 \times 13 = 169 \Rightarrow 12 \times 14 = 168$	$71 \times 71 = 5041 \Rightarrow 70 \times 72 = 5040$
$5 \times 5 = 25 \Rightarrow 4 \times 6 = 24$	$14 \times 14 = 196 \Rightarrow 13 \times 15 = 195$	$50 \times 50 = 2500 \Rightarrow 49 \times 51 = 2499$
$6 \times 6 = 36 \Rightarrow 5 \times 7 = 35$	$15 \times 15 = 225 \Rightarrow 14 \times 16 = 224$	$23 \times 23 = 529 \Rightarrow 22 \times 24 = 528$
$7 \times 7 = 49 \Rightarrow 6 \times 8 = 48$	$16 \times 16 = 256 \Rightarrow 15 \times 17 = 255$	$37 \times 37 = 1369 \Rightarrow 36 \times 38 = 1368$
$8 \times 8 = 64 \Rightarrow 7 \times 9 = 63$	$17 \times 17 = 289 \Rightarrow 16 \times 18 = 288$	$64 \times 64 = 4096 \Rightarrow 63 \times 65 = 4095$
$9 \times 9 = 81 \Rightarrow 8 \times 10 = 80$	$18 \times 18 = 324 \Rightarrow 17 \times 19 = 323$	$30 \times 30 = 900 \Rightarrow 29 \times 31 = 899$
$75 \times 75 = 5625 \Rightarrow 74 \times 76 = 5624$	$19 \times 19 = 361 \Rightarrow 18 \times 20 = 360$	$44 \times 44 = 1936 \Rightarrow 43 \times 45 = 1935$
$67 \times 67 = 4489 \Rightarrow 66 \times 68 = 4488$	$20 \times 20 = 400 \Rightarrow 19 \times 21 = 399$	$83 \times 83 = 6889 \Rightarrow 82 \times 84 = 6888$
$103 \times 103 = 10609 \Rightarrow 102 \times 104 = 10608$	$2000 \times 2000 = 4000000 \Rightarrow 1999 \times 2001 = 3999999$	
$5236989632 \times 5236989632 = 27426060405675495 \Rightarrow 5236989631 \times 5236989633 = 27426060405675494$		

As observed, this relation has held true for all the numbers tested.

Conclusion:

The introduced law shows that in the multiplication of natural numbers, there are still hidden and beautiful relationships that can be inspiring in teaching basic mathematical concepts. In future research, it will be examined whether this law can also be extended to the sets of integers or real numbers.

Keywords: Natural numbers, multiplication, numerical pattern, mathematical law, mathematics education.